

FLIGHT REPORT A257
TIGER
27/5/93

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 FLIGHT REPORT A258 27/05/93 TIGER

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading	
10:05:05				TAKE OFF FARNBOROUGH			
		Transit to Kinloss at FL090					
11:31:57	(3)	11:45:17	(6)	PROFILE P1	FL090 -	50ft	355/020
11:51:51				LAND AT RAF KINLOSS			
12:03:11				TAKE OFF RAF KINLOSS			
12:05:34	(7)	12:13:28	(8)	PROFILE P2	500' -	FL050	020
12:23:42	(9)	12:31:16	(15)	RUN 1.1	FL060		007
12:37:58	(18)	12:43:58	(22)	RUN 1.2	FL060		180
12:44:33	(23)	12:51:04	(26)	RUN 1.3	FL060		130/090
13:00:28	(30)	13:06:43	(33)	RUN 2.1	1500' agl		015
13:06:43	(33)	13:10:11	(36)	RUN 2.2	1500' agl		285
13:11:35	(37)	13:17:54	(41)	RUN 2.3	1500' agl		180
13:25:10	(44)	13:30:45	(47)	RUN 2.4	1500' agl		090/270
13:34:08	(49)	13:40:09	(52)	RUN 2.5	1500' agl		015
13:41:06	(53)	13:43:55	(56)	RUN 2.6	1500' agl		285
13:45:21	(57)	13:51:42	(60)	RUN 2.7	1500' agl		190
13:58:22	(61)	14:03:53	(64)	RUN 2.8	1500' agl		090/300
14:05:52	(65)	14:12:58	(68)	RUN 2.9	1500' agl		015
14:13:45	(69)	14:18:21	(71)	RUN 2.10	1500' agl		270
14:18:21	(71)	14:25:10	(75)	RUN 2.11	1500' agl		180
14:30:26	(76)	14:34:40	(79)	RUN 3.1	500' agl		090/270
14:36:27	(80)	14:43:20	(84)	RUN 3.2	500' agl		010
14:43:52	(86)	14:48:12	(88)	RUN 3.3	500' agl		270
14:51:29	(89)	14:57:35	(93)	RUN 3.4	500' agl		180
15:03:25	(94)	15:08:06	(98)	RUN 3.5	500' agl		090/270
15:09:44	(100)	15:16:43	(101)	RUN 3.6	500' agl		010
15:18:10	(104)	15:22:34	(107)	RUN 3.7	500' agl		270
15:22:34	(107)	15:29:46	(111)	RUN 3.8	500' agl		180
15:38:00	(112)	15:42:00	(117)	RUN 4.1	250' agl		010
15:43:30	(118)	15:47:15	(123)	RUN 4.2	250' agl		190
15:49:01	(124)	15:54:57	(126)	RUN 4.3	250' agl		010
15:56:39	(127)	16:07:34	(129)	RUN 5.1	1500' agl		180
16:17:03				LAND AT WICK			

A257 27 - MAY - 93 GPS data Times: 08:10:02 - 16:24:33

TIGER II

Methane emission experiment

MAY-JUNE 1993

Boundary layer budget study

Study area

Catthross-Sutherland
(CROSS) aircraft experiment

Thursday 27 May

Objective -

detection of methane emission
from point wetlands over regional flux

10 bags per circuit
1 x 500', 3 x 1000' 2 x 500'

Event number	GMT	BAG	Location	comment
Row 1. 10	12 24 59	H31	start bag 1. 6R	collat ~ 6 R ft 1831
11	27 04	H32	" 1	
12	28 10	H33		1819
13	29 06	H34		1820
14	30 15	H35		1822
16	31 20	H36		↑ 1847
17	32 50	H37	over water - N.	20 spc per bag 1844
18	38 30	H38		↓ 1828
20	39 50	H39		30 spc per bag 1836
21	41 40	H13	over water puts	1858
Row 2. 27	54 00	H41	OVER SEA	1500 ft 1870
28	55 12	H42	"	1500 ft 1866
2.1 29	13 00 12	H43	OVER LAND	" 1871
30	01 32	H44	"	" 1842
32	02 50	H45	over "	" 1843
2.2 34	08 12	H46	OVER SEA	" 1850
35	09 48	H47	"	Wind E/NE 1844
2.3 38	13 44	H48	OVER LAND	" 1848
39	14 48	H49	"	" 1850
40	16 48	H50	"	" 1843
2.4 45	25 32	H51	OVER SEA	1500 ft 1842
46	26 50	H52	"	" 1841

Event number	GMT	BAG	LOCATION	COMMENT
2.5 48	33 13	H 53	OVER LAND	1500 ft 1852
50	34 25	H 54	"	" 1851
50 51	38 30	H 55	OVER " site	" 1852
2.6 52/4	41.40	H 56	OVER SEA N	" 1854
53	43.02	H 57	"	" 1847
2.7 58	47.37	H 58	OVER LAND	" 1855
59	49.00	H 59	"	" 1846
60	51 30	H 60	"	" 1848
2.8 62	59 50	H 61	OVER SEA	1500 ft 1850
63	14 00 50	H 62	"	" 1847
2.9 65	06 00	H 63	OVER LANDS	" 1850
66	08 38	H 64	"	" 1848
67	09 30	H 65	OVER LAND	" 1865
2.10 69	14 10	H 66	OVER SEA N	1500 ft 1861
70	15 32 ⁰⁰	H 67	"	" 1857
2.11 72	14 21 20	H 68	OVER LAND N	1500 ft 1852
73	23 -00	H 69	"	" 1848
74	24 30	H 70		
77	14 31 30	H 71	over sea	500 ft ① 1850
78	14 32 50	H 72	"	" 1855
80	14 38 48	H 73	over land S	500 1872
82	14 37 55	H 74	"	" 1848 1874
83	14 39 28	H 75	"	500 1854
84	14 45 27	H 76	over sea	500 1845
87	14 46.00	H 77	" "	"
90	14 53.45	H 78	over land N	500
91	14 54 50	H 79	" " "	1865
92	14 55 20	H 80	" " "	500

Event marker	GMT	Bag	Location	Comment	
95	1504.00	81	over Sea	500 ft 1863	
96	1505.07	82		500	
99	1509.50	83	over land	500 - 1863	
01	1510.20	84	" "	500 1856	
02	1510.40	85	" "	500 1863	
05	1518.20	86	over Sea	500 1857	
06	1518.55	87	over Sea	500 1859	
08	?	88	over land N	500 Bag full green 1851	
09	?	89	" "	500 green 1851	
10	1528.00	90	" "	500 1850	
13		91	over bag	} 250 R1	1848
14		92			1843
15		93			1843
16		94			1843
17		95			1845
18		96		} 250 R2	1844
19		97			1843
20		98			1847
21		99			1847
22	1547.50	100			1850

2 BAGS OVER SEA
(6 to 10 min)

STREATHYPS

DUNNET HEAD

3 bags

3 bags

EXPERIMENTAL SITE

START

70 km.
16 min

50 km 10 min

30 km over sea
5 km min

2 BAGS OVER SEA
6 min

FLIGHT REPORT:

FLIGHT REPORT A258 28/05/93 TIGER

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading		
09:57:35				TAKE OFF WICK				
10:04:55	(1)	10:10:29	(2)	PROFILE P1	50ft -	FL060	320	
10:12:00	(3)	10:20:55	(14)	RUN 1	FL060		330 Sea	
10:25:08	(15)	10:26:58	(19)	RUN 2	500'		160 Sea	
10:36:51	(20)	10:44:03	(30)	RUN 3	500' agl		175 Land	
10:45:01	(31)	10:51:59	(40)	RUN 4	2000' agl		345 Land	
10:54:02	(41)	10:58:50	(46)	RUN 5	2000'		340 Sea	
		Transit to point A at FL070 (55.559N 0.203E)						
11:49:45	(49)	11:58:27	(59)	RUN 6	FL075		135 Sea	
12:16:58	(60)	12:29:02	(61)	PROFILE P2	FL075 -	50 ft	225/240 Sea	
12:31:48	(62)	12:40:14	(81)	RUN 7	500'		275/170 Sea	
13:34:20				LAND AT FARNBOROUGH				

A258 28 - MAY - 93

GPS data
Times: 08:41:51 - 13:38:26

28 May 1993

TIGER II methano
Experiment II

- Objective
- (1) 10 BAGS clean air above boundary layer over sea 6000'
 - (2) 3 BAGS over sea 500'
 - (3) 7 BAGS over bay N → S run, 500'
 - (4) 7 BAGS over bay S → N run ~~500~~ 2000'
 - (5) 3 BAGS over sea (W coast) 2000'

TRANSIT to N. Sea off E coast Scotland

- (6) 10 Bags air crossing altitude 8000' ? (5 seconds)
- (7) 20 Bags off Lincs/West coast 500'

Event number	GMT	BAG	Location	Comment
1	10 12 10			
4	10 12 12	41	OVER SEA	6000' over sea
5	13 12	42	"	"
6	13 52	43	"	"
7	14 33	44	"	"
8	15 18	45	"	"
9	16 24	46	"	"
10	17 10	47	"	"
11	18 02	48	"	"
12	18 40	49	"	"
13	19 13	50	"	"
ROW 2.	10 25 08			
16	10 25 12	51		over sea 500 ft.
17	25 56	52		"
18	28 23	53		"
20	10 26 51			
21	32 23	54	OVER FARM	over bog 500
22	38 29	55	OVER BOG	
23	38 55	56	"	
24	39 19	57		
25	39 42	58		
26	40 00	59		
27	40 21	60		
28	41 35	61	FILLED TWO MORE BAGS OVER BOG RS-W TOO QUICK!	OVER SITE 500 ft
29	41 54	62		"
31 ROW 4	10 45 01			
32	46 58	63		OVER BOG 200 ft.
32	47 28	64	OVER SITE	
34	47 55	65		
35	48 20	66		
36	48 44	67		

Point marker	GMT	BAG	LOCATION	COMMENT
		67		over bag
37	49 10	68		OVER Bay area
38	49 24	69		OVER Bay.
39	49 44	70		OVER Bay
Row 5. 41	10 54 02			
43	57 23	71		over sea. 2 2000 ' (A)
44	57 41	72		"
45	58 14	73		"
Row 6. 69	11-49-45.			
50	11-50-10	74	OVER SEA	OVER SEA 2000 ft.
51	50 51	75	"	7500 ft
52	51 31	76	"	"
53	52 24	77	"	"
54	53 21	78	"	"
55	54 20	79	"	"
56	55 22	80	"	"
57	56 21	81	"	"
58	57 21	82	"	" } 500' off Lurekash cross
Row 7				
62	12-31-48	82		OVER SEA.
63	31-54	83		
64	32-18	84		
65	32 44	85		
66	33 08	86		
67	33 34	87		
68	34 00	88		
69	34 25	89		
70	34 55	90		

Event number	GMT	BAG	LOCATION	COMMENT
71	35-35	91		500' over sea
72	36-04	92		Luic'ushie
73	36-30	93		
74	36-58	94		
75	37-28	95		
76	37-55	96		
77	38-28	97		
78	38 59	98		
79	39 23	99		
80	39 49	100		

FLIGHT REPORT A259 03/06/93 TIGER

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading	
10:30:23				TAKE OFF FARNBOROUGH			
				Transit to Lossimouth at FL085			
11:52:46	(3)	11:58:59	(4)	PROFILE P1	FL085 - 2000'	350	
12:02:15				LAND AT RAF LOSSIMOUTH			
12:21:11				TAKE OFF RAF LOSSIMOUTH			
12:24:46	(5)	12:36:01	(6)	PROFILE P2	50ft - 6000'	010	
12:51:42	(7)	12:59:14	(8)	RUN 1	500' agl	180	intercom
13:00:24	(9)	13:06:47	(10)	RUN 2	2000' msl	005	intercom
13:11:06	(12)	13:15:20	(17)	RUN 3	250' agl	185	Land
13:18:08	(18)	13:20:39	(24)	RUN 4	100' agl	007	Land
13:26:09	(25)	13:33:01	(31)	RUN 5	500' agl	180	Land
13:37:33	(36)	13:43:51	(41)	RUN 6	500' agl	007	Land
13:45:27	(42)	13:55:09	(51)	RUN 7	100' msl	330	Sea SS:3
14:02:21	(52)	14:14:14	(60)	RUN 8	500' msl	205	Sea
14:15:36	(61)	14:46:03	(75)	RUN 9	500' msl	025/145	Sea
14:56:59	(76)	15:06:32	(87)	RUN 10	500' msl	210	Sea
15:12:43	(89)	15:21:34	(96)	RUN 11	500' msl	030/360	Sea
15:24:58	(97)	15:34:21	(98)	PROFILE P3	50ft - FL060	280	Sea SS:4/5
15:36:16	(99)	15:47:05	(111)	RUN 12	FL060	165/270	Sea/Land
15:54:55				LAND AT WICK			

A259 03-JUN-93

GPS data
Times:08:21:58-16:01:33

EVENT	GMT	BAG	LOCATION	COMMENT
94	516.49	31		OVER SEA cont of RUN 11.
100	153844	32		RUN 12 153616 {6000' Background}
101	153940	33		OVER SITE.
102	4010	34		
103	4053	35		1845-1850
104	4204	36		
105	4255	37		
106	4323	38		
107	4357	39		
108	154450	26		
109	154500	26		
11	131027	41		RUN 3 131106
13	131130	42		over bog (1) 2500' N ↓
14	131212	43		
15	131247	44		
16	131350	45		
19	131810	46		RUN 4 131808
20	131840	47		100ft over bog (2) S ↑
21	131909	48		
22	131934	49		
23	132004	50		
26	132705	51		RUN 5 132609
27	2739	52		WIND 140° 20kts
28	2802	53		over bog (2)
29	2836	54		
30	2905	55		
32	3521	56		RUN 6 133733
33	3542	57		S.
34	3626	58		
35	3704	59		
37	3741	60		

SWT	GMT	BAS	LOCATION	COMMENT
38	39 00	61		500 ft OVER SITE, 100 ft → S → N
39	39 29	62		
40	39 56	63		
43	46 00	64	RUN 7 13 45 27	ON TRANSIT TO 59.5°N 4.5°W BACKGROUND 100 ft
44	46 31	65		OVER SEA, heads N.
45	47 06	66		
46	47 50	67		
47	48 29	68		
48	49 24	69		
49	49 56	70		
53	14 02 27	71	RUN 8 14 02 21	500 ft 59.5°N 5°W
54	14 08 47	72		CARE WARM ↓ to SKYE W
55	14 05 32	73		
56	07 32	74		
57	09 32	75		
58	11 32	76		Sampling in rain
59	13 50	77		u
62	14 17 12	78	RUN 9 14 18 36	Turn and head North start sampling when rain stops.
63	22 44	79	WIND 230°	
64	24 40	80		
65	26 43	81	WIND 185 KTS	
66	28 35	82		
67	30 37	83	WIND 154	
68	32 37	84		
69	34 36	85		
70	36 37	86	140° WIND	
71	38 33	87		
72	40 35	88		
73	14 42 34	89	154 KTS	
74	44 35	90		BAS SPLIT. NO SAMPLE

SHEWT GWT BAG LOCATION COMMENT

77	57 00	91
78	58 00	92
79	59 00	93
80	15 00 03	94
81	01 01	95
82	02 02	96
83	03 00	97
84	04 00	98
85	05 01	99
86	06 02	100

RUN 10
146659

off E coast 500' W of AW

89	12 43	27
90	13 30	28
91	14 55	29
93	15 45	30

RUN 11
151239

09	15 45 12	BB5
10	15 46 46	END.

cont of run 12
5000 ft

FLIGHT REPORT A260 04/06/93 TIGER

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading		
09:52:06				TAKE OFF WICK				
09:54:50	(1)	10:06:22	(2)	PROFILE P1	50ft -	FL070	202	Sea SS:2/3
10:07:25	(3)	10:12:58	(14)	RUN 1	FL070		065	Sea
10:16:57	(15)	10:25:49	(26)	RUN 2	500'		345/225	Sea
10:32:00	(27)	10:49:08	(39)	RUN 3	500'		300	Sea
10:52:17	(40)	11:19:03	(53)	RUN 4	500'		220	Sea
11:20:32	(54)	11:27:58	(55)	PROFILE P2	50ft -	FL050	215	Sea 500/min
11:28:45	(56)	11:30:58	(57)	restart P2	FL050 -	FL075	150	Sea 1000/"
		Transit to North Sea		FL075				
12:16:34	(59)	12:19:00	(64)	RUN 4	FL075		135	Sea
12:20:35	(65)	12:28:46	(66)	PROFILE P3	FL075 -	50 ft	165	Sea SS 2/3
12:30:28	(67)	13:12:20	(92)	RUN 6	500'		155	Sea
13:13:14	(93)	13:21:09	(94)	PROFILE P4	500' -	FL085	155	Sea 500/min
13:24:03	(98)	13:25:25	(101)	RUN 7	FL060		250	Sea/Land
14:04:53				LAND AT FARNBOROUGH				

A260 04-JUN-93

GPS data
Times:08:44:04-14:08:10

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EVENT Number	GMT	BAR	Location	Comment
04	10 07 36	31	2020	Run 1 / 10-07-25.
05	08 04	32	1840	Background 6000' 'wick' as fast as poss
06	08 31	33	1970	
07	09 02	34	1835	
08	09 30	35	1905	
09	10 11	36	1894	
10	10 44	37	1842	
11	11 18	38	1840	
12	11 48	39	1844	
13	12 19	40 (26)	1842	
16	17 09	41	1945	
17	17 32	42	1953	E coast of Cuthren 500' sample as fast as possible
18	18 00	43	1950	
19	18 23	44	1940	
20	19 00	45	1945	
21	19 38	46	1936	
22	20 15	47	1940	
23	21 13	48	1952	
24	22 06	49	1960	
25	22 00	50	1964	
28	10-32-10	51	2004	
29	10 34 31	52	2011	o Sutherland
30	10 37 06	53	1890	500'
31	10 38 48	54	1880	1 bag every 2 mins (ask Andrew for ETA at end of run)
32	10 39 53	55	1875	
34	10 41 36	56	1919	
35	42 40	57		
36	43 49	58	1881	
37	45 40	59	1980	
38	47 05	60	1890	

EVENT	RUNT	BAG	LOCATION	Comments
41	10 52 44	61	1884	Run 4 / 10-32-17 West Coast of Sutherland
42	55 03	62	1880 IN RAIN.	500'
43	58 01	63	1920	1 bag every 2 mins
44	11 01 00	64	1880	
45	04 01	65	1870	
46	07 01	66	1878	
48	10 01	67	1952	
49	13 01	68	1975	
50	16 57	69	1907	
51	17 04	70	1838 1875	
59	12 16 34	71	1842	Run 5. 12-16-34
60	17 10	72	1837	6000' off E coast
61	17 34	73	1835	'Newcastle'
62	18 01	74	1838	fast sampling
63	18 32	75	1852	
68	12 30 28	76	2090	Run 6 12 30 28 E coast
69	31 37	77	2015 2060	500'
70	33 00	78	2015	1 bag every 2 mins
71	34 35	79	2000	1 bag every 2 mins fill bags slow
72	36 10	80	2015	
73	37 45	81	1950	
74	39 20	82	1935	
75	40 55	83	1930	
76	42-30	84	1948	
77	44 05	85	1971	
78	45 40	86	1948	
79	47 15	87	1930	
80	49 00	88	<hr/> Blind	
81	51 00	89	1928	
82	53 00	90	1930	

EVENT	QMT	BAG	LOCATION	
83	55 00	91	1920	
84	57 00	92	2000	
85	59 00	93	1910	E coast
86	13 01 00	94	1887	MARKS - LINES 500'
87	13 03 00	95	1880	
88	13 05 00	96	1865	
89	13 07 00	97	1918	
90	13 09 00	98	1458	
91	11 00	99	1848	
95	13 22 33	100	1839	RUN 7/
96	13 23 13			
97	27 43	27	?	
		28	1867	5000' at end of profile after E coast measurements
99	24 20	29	1847	
100	24 31	30	1843	